

D7.2

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy

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Disclaimer and acknowledgement

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Executive summary

Strategic and well-planned communications are crucial to any research project willing to impact the surrounding society. To create societal impact, a research project needs to have shared and clear guidelines for its communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

This deliverable has nine sections that entail a comprehensive account of the methods adopted in GRETA for communication, dissemination, and exploitation. Section 1 introduces the deliverable, meaning of CDE and the objectives of the strategy. Section 2 lists project GRETA's communication, dissemination, and exploitation objectives. Section 3 describes the key elements of GRETA's project identity. Section 4 focuses on target groups and stakeholders of GRETA's CDE activities. Section 5 lists all the channels and tools the project uses. Section 6 describes the communication and dissemination activities planned. Section 7 introduces the project's social media strategy. Section 8 introduces the project's exploitation strategy. Section 9 lists all the metrics and measures of success that are used to follow GRETA's CDE activities.

GRETA's Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy will be updated when needed, and it serves as the CDE guide for all project partners.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CDE:	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Dx.x:	Deliverable number
E-COM:	Executive Committee
EEAB:	External Expert Advisory Board
EU:	European Union
GRETA:	GR ^e en Energy Transition Actions
NGO:	Non-governmental organization
OPCE:	GRETA Open Portfolio for Civic Energy Empowerment

1 Introduction

1.1 What is a communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy?

Project GRETA aims to significantly further the EU climate-neutrality objectives. For this to happen, the project needs to reach out to multiple audiences, interact with various stakeholders, create understanding, and ensure that its results are seen, heard, and utilized.

Communications is the key for societal impact. Every research project aiming to influence the society needs a comprehensive strategy for well-planned and timely communications. This strategy defines the objectives, target groups, channels, means and indicators for GRETA's communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

The European Commission's Horizon 2020 program has defined three different spheres for research project communications. The spheres are:

Communication

Communication means all the activities that aim to make the project and its developments known from the very beginning until the end of the project. Communication includes the project brand and presence in different communication channels.

Dissemination

Dissemination means all the activities that aim to spread information on the project results. Dissemination is usually done through different kind of reports, briefs, and publications.

Exploitation

Exploitation means all the activities that aim to use the project results outside the project. Exploitation is usually done by conducting further research, drafting new policies, creating commercial applications, or using the results in education.

This strategy considers all the three spheres of research project communications. The strategy was created by KAS and contributed by all project partners. It will be updated if needed.

1.2 Objectives of the deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is:

- to define objectives, target groups and channels for GRETA's communication, dissemination, and exploitation
- to describe the methods used in project promotion, interaction, and dissemination
- to encourage project partners to adopt project key messages, tone-of-voice, channels, and tools
- to offer a strategic basis for detailed communication, dissemination, and exploitation plans

This deliverable is also a communications guide for all GRETA partners.

2 Communication, dissemination, and exploitation objectives

2.1 Communication objectives

Project GRETA's main communication objectives are:

C1 to promote and raise awareness and interest in the project, its progress and results as well as themes related to energy citizenship

C2 to create interaction and understanding with the stakeholders of their needs and the project's benefits to them to ensure the usability of the results

2.2 Dissemination objectives

Project GRETA's main dissemination objectives are:

D1 to share knowledge and recommendations to policymakers on energy citizenship and how it can be promoted to support the energy transition

D2 to provide citizens and communities information to help them evaluate and compare their current energy behaviors, and thus to find the most suitable sustainable energy strategies for them

D3 to increase and improve the interaction between citizens and policymakers on energy-related matters to support the energy transition

D4 to make the project results available for exploitation beyond the lifetime of the project

2.3 Exploitation objectives

Strategically planned exploitation ensures the sustainability of the project's results beyond its lifetime. The aim of exploitation is to translate the results into concrete value and impact on society. GRETA's main exploitation objectives are:

E1 to make the results available for use in further research activities via scientific publications and conferences

E2 to use the results in education offered to the future energy and climate professionals by the academic partners of the consortium

E3 to formulate policy recommendations and guidelines to policymakers on energy citizenship and its impact on the energy transition

E4 to create awareness of societal change by helping the case study participants to get involved in different participatory processes of project GRETA and to exploit the results in the development of their own energy strategies

3 Target groups and stakeholders

This section lists GRETA's most important target groups and stakeholders. The project stakeholders were also listed in the deliverable D7.1, Stakeholder Engagement Framework.

3.1 Communication and dissemination target groups and stakeholders

Case study participants

Each GRETA case study has a unique socio-cultural context and a set of case study participants. The case study participants mostly include the consumers and prosumers of energy: residents, property owners, business owners, cooperatives, and communities in the case study countries.

GRETA will plan communication and engagement activities to ensure that case study participants are actively involved in the case studies. Case study participants will be provided with understandable and practical information on energy efficiency and clean energy solutions. The communication and dissemination activities aim to increase case study participants' awareness and understanding of energy citizenship.

Local, regional, national, and EU-level decision-makers

Policymakers and regulatory authorities in the case study cities, regions, countries and on the EU level are an important part of all GRETA case studies and the implementation of the project results. Communication and dissemination activities will be targeted mainly to policymakers and decision-makers who work with urban planning, energy solutions, mobility, and sustainable development. This target and stakeholder group includes, for example, municipal decision-makers in Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Spain.

Policymakers and decision-makers will be provided with information on energy citizenship, its benefits and impacts on the achievement of decarbonization goals. This target and stakeholder group will be deeply involved in the case studies and in co-designing of the policy recommendations.

Businesses and the industry

GRETA will provide the energy industry and businesses with information on the energy citizenship phenomena, collected data and the commercial opportunities and challenges it poses. Businesses and the industry include, for example, local energy providers and cooperatives. Local businesses are consulted and involved in the co-designing of the case studies.

Academic community

GRETA will communicate its objectives, progress, methods, and results to researchers interested in the social aspects of the energy transition. GRETA will also contact and cooperate with other research projects that focus on clean energy transition. These projects include, for example, COMETS, DIALOGUES, EC2, ENCLUDE, EnergyPROSPECTS, SOCIALRES, ParCos, BRIGHT, POCITYF and SONNET.

Non-governmental organizations, non-profits, and international networks

GRETA provides NGOs with updated information on energy citizenship and energy communities. The NGOs GRETA wishes to reach out to are mainly organizations that work with topics related to sustainability and energy. These organizations include, for example, local housing agencies and energy and welfare associations. The information and collected data can help NGOs to better serve communities and citizens. GRETA will also benefit highly from the information and experiences NGOs and non-profits have from the local communities.

GRETA also follows closely and discusses energy-related matters within different international networks and events. These networks include, for example, REScoop.eu, EU Sustainable Energy Week, the COP26, ECOLISE, World Energy Council and ERRIN.

International and local media

International and local media outlets are important for raising the awareness of the general public and policymakers. GRETA will be in contact with journalists in each case study country to offer updated information on energy citizenship and case studies. The project will contact journalists and media outlets that have previously covered energy and sustainability-related topics.

External Expert Advisory Board

The project has appointed an external expert advisory board, also known as EEAB. The EEAB is composed of key stakeholders and experts in domains that are vital for the project, such as energy systems, energy policy and sustainability; urban innovation and development; public governance; ethics, diversity, data privacy, and IPR; civil society; green mobility, and social and human behavioral aspects. The EEAB helps to disseminate the project results through their networks. The EEAB members are invited to participate in the project events.

3.2 Exploitation target groups and stakeholders

Researchers

The project partners will publish and disseminate the project results through academic conferences and scientific journals. The project results will then be used in further research activities related to energy citizenship and energy communities.

Students in the partner universities

The academic project partners will use the project results in their university courses.

Local, regional, national, and EU-level decision-makers

GRETA creates policy recommendations targeted to decision-makers.

Recommendations will help to create policies that enhance energy citizenship.

Case study participants

The case study participants will be offered different kinds of tools and information on sustainable energy choices. This will lead to sustainable behavior patterns and citizen-led initiatives.

NGOs and businesses

The data used and collected in the project will be further used by different organizations and experts to develop their services.

4 Project identity

GRETA's project identity includes the elements that make the project sound, look, and feel like GRETA. A project identity includes key messages, slogan, logo, and visual identity of the project. These elements make the project recognizable and convey GRETA's mission to its target groups and stakeholders.

4.1 Key messages

Key messages help the project partners to communicate the project's purpose, activities, and goals in a consistent way throughout different communication channels and organizations. Key messages are the building blocks of the project's communication. However, they can be modified to serve the specific needs and interests of different target groups as well as to consider the different stages of the project.

In the beginning of the project, the key messages will focus on the project's purpose, activities, and goals. In the later stages of the project, the key messages will focus more on the project's results.

The short version of GRETA's key message is:

GRETA is paving the way to active energy citizenship within the EU's energy communities, to accelerate the energy transition. We are a research project funded by the European Commission from 2021 to 2023.

The longer version of GRETA's key message is:

The EU aims to reach climate neutrality by 2050. This goal can only be achieved if citizens play their role and are given equal opportunity to act towards it.

We are GRETA, a research project funded by the European Commission, paving the way to active energy citizenship within energy communities. Energy citizenship means that every one of us can participate in the energy transition, by adopting and promoting sustainable energy behaviors.

GRETA studies the social side of the energy transition. We want to understand how energy citizenship works in different contexts and geographical levels. What kind of knowledge, social structures, access to technology and financial resources are needed to make an active energy citizen?

From 2021 to 2023, we will be working with energy communities in Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Spain. Citizens in these communities will adopt renewable energy technologies and electric vehicles, monitor their efficient energy behaviors, and participate in the sustainable planning of mobility, both within their cities and internationally.

We create community decarbonization pathways based on collaborative roadmaps for behavioral change and supported by trust-based social agreements. Our findings will help European-wide policymakers encourage active citizen participation in the energy transition.

4.2 Tone-of-voice

Tone-of-voice describes the way GRETA communicates in its own external communication channels used for promotional purposes. It is a description of what GRETA feels and sounds like to the broader public audiences. The tone-of-voice does not apply to scientific publications, policy briefs or other material produced for specific expert audiences.

GRETA's tone-of-voice consists of four elements:

Understandable

GRETA aims to ensure that the project's message is heard despite differences in cultural background and level of education. In its external communication, GRETA uses understandable and accessible language, i.e., avoids abbreviations, project jargon, difficult scientific terms, and inaccurate language.

Friendly

GRETA wants to come across as approachable and respectful. GRETA's stakeholders and target groups are an important part of the project. GRETA aims to show them that their time, resources, and input are highly valued.

Hopeful

GRETA's mission is to offer solutions and visions of a brighter future. However, the project avoids cutting corners and coming across as falsely positive.

Trustworthy

The information GRETA shares is based on academic research.

4.3 Language choices

English is the main communication language of project GRETA. English is used in the project's main communication channels and materials (e.g., website, social media channels and newsletters).

Other languages are used in the project's communication and interaction with local, regional, and national stakeholders within the consortium partner countries. Communication materials are translated into local languages when needed. Local project partners are responsible for the translations.

4.4 Logo

Project GRETA's logo (Figure 1) was designed to illustrate the future in an inspiring and playful way. The logo consists of two parts. The yellow illustration is called a symbol. Two figures are holding hands, and together they form the shape of a lightning, symbolizing energy. The text element is the project acronym. The logo is used alongside the EU emblem in all the project templates and documents.

Figure 1. Project logo

4.5 Visual elements

GRETA's visual elements (Figure 2) include a color palette, fonts, illustrations, document templates, and an image bank. GRETA's color palette is positive, fresh, smart, and simple. The main colors are yellow, light blue and grey. An additional color palette of secondary colors has been designed with accessibility, charts, and graphs in mind.

GRETA has five illustrations that represent the energy transition, energy citizenship, energy communities, the project, and its results. The illustrations are used in the project templates, website, and social media channels.

Literata

Subhead Regular Abcdefg 123456

Subhead Italic Abcdefg 123456

LITERATA

Used for headlines, lead paragraphs and other large-sized text. It can also be used as body text in long format layout.

Tablet Gothic

Light Abcdefg 123456

Regular Abcdefg 123456

Bold Abcdefg 123456

TABLET GOTHIC

Used for body text and smaller headlines.

Figure 2. Examples of some of the visual elements

4.6 Slogan and key visual

GRETA's slogan is "You've got the power". The slogan captures GRETA's core: the empowerment of citizens. The word "power" has two meanings: the power to influence and the power of sustainable energy. The slogan is used in social media and promotional material like brochures and stickers. It can be accompanied by GRETA's key message.

The slogan can be combined with an illustration to form GRETA's key visual (Figure 3). The key visual will be used in promotional materials like brochures, roll-ups, and stickers.

You've got the power

Figure 3. GRETA's key visual

5 Channels and tools

Project GRETA uses various channels and tools in its communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Different channels and tools are used to ensure that GRETA's communication activities reach all the different stakeholders.

5.1 Project website

The project website is published at the beginning of the project in M6. Before the final project website is published, a temporary one-pager website has been used to provide the basic information about the project, from M2 onwards.

The project website is targeted at all the stakeholders who are interested in GRETA and want to find out more about the project.

The website offers information on the project's:

- goals, timeline, and outputs
- research questions and topics
- partners
- case studies
- contact information and
- funding.

On the website, the project will publish and link:

- GRETA OPCE which contains the frameworks, models and data created in the project
- latest scientific articles, policy briefs, deliverables, media coverage, and presentations
- blog posts (also including news and events)
- links to the project's social media channels and a newsletter subscription form
- link to the GRETA community for the case study participants

The website URL is <https://projectgreta.eu/>.

The website is maintained and updated by KAS.

5.2 Social media

Twitter

The project's Twitter communication is executed via its own Twitter profile [@ProjectGRETA](#). Project partners and individual project members are also encouraged to use their own Twitter profiles to communicate with the project's stakeholders and to share content about GRETA.

Communication in Twitter is targeted, and connections are created especially to the scientific community, policymakers on different levels, journalists, NGOs and associations, and energy providers, retailers, and operators. Twitter is used to share knowledge on the project's development, recent news, events, and results of the project as well as information on the topic of energy citizenship and its role in the energy transition. The project uses Twitter also to interact with its stakeholders.

The project's Twitter profile is updated by KAS.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is used mainly to disseminate information on the project's results and to reach out to potential industrial and academic partners. General information about the project is also shared on LinkedIn.

The project's LinkedIn communication is executed via its LinkedIn page [Project GRETA](#). The consortium partners and individual project members are also encouraged to use their own LinkedIn profiles and pages to engage in dialogue with GRETA's stakeholders and share content about GRETA.

The project's LinkedIn page is updated by KAS.

"GRETA community" Facebook group

A Facebook group is created as the base for the GRETA community to which all the case study participants are invited. In the community, the case study participants can share information, learnings and best practices on their energy behavior strategies and interact with the consortium members. The community is promoted to the case study participants especially in the beginning of the case studies.

The Facebook group is moderated by KAS.

YouTube

A YouTube channel is created for the project where all the videos produced in the project can be downloaded. The videos will be shared mainly through linking or embedding in other communication channels.

The project's YouTube channel is updated by KAS.

ResearchGate

GRETA is registered to ResearchGate. The project members are encouraged to distribute their publications, conference papers and policy briefs in ResearchGate. [The project profile](#) is updated by LUT.

Other social media channels and platforms

The project partners may use other social media channels and platforms (e.g., WhatsApp, Telegram) to communicate directly with the case study participants or other collaborators in the project. These channels are used only for communication within small and closed groups, not for public communication.

5.3 Promotional materials

Brochures

GRETA produces brochures that are distributed to the case study participants, decision-makers and general audience in workshops, seminars, and other events. The first GRETA brochure was produced in M4. Its function is to offer general information on the project and its goals.

Videos

Videos are used to raise awareness of the project and energy citizenship. They are mainly targeted to the general audience and distributed through GRETA's social media channels. The first video will be produced in M6. The video is used to promote the project for GRETA's stakeholders and target groups.

Roll-ups

Roll-ups are used in academic and non-academic events. They are present in all external project workshops and seminars that take place face-to-face. GRETA roll-up will be designed in M6–M7.

Other promotional materials

Other promotional materials, for example laptop stickers and shoppers, are produced for different events that aim to promote the project to the general audience and case study participants. Other promotional materials may also include visual materials, such as banners, that can be used in digital channels.

5.4 E-newsletter

The project has a e-newsletter targeted to all target and stakeholder groups. It is sent approximately twice a year and includes the latest blog posts, event invitations, project news and materials. Every case study, workshop and seminar participant is encouraged to subscribe to GRETA's newsletter. The project uses Mailchimp

newsletter platform and newsletters are produced and sent by KAS. KAS will consult the project partners before sending the newsletters.

5.5 Events and conferences

Events

GRETA will be present in relevant events organized by the project's stakeholders and in events organized in the field of GRETA's research. Case studies will be present in local events that will help to promote the project and engage case study participants. The events can be organized either as physical or virtual events. Participation as a project in EU level events, such as EU Sustainable Energy Week 2021, will be decided by the GRETA E-COM.

Academic conferences

The project partners and members participate in multiple conferences, seminars, and research days during the project. The goal is to promote the project and disseminate the project results to the scientific community. Conferences also offer opportunities to collaborate with other researchers and projects.

5.6 Media relations

Press releases

The project publishes press releases approximately twice a year. Press releases are produced by KAS together with the project partners. GRETA E-COM accepts the press releases and decides on the distribution. The releases include information about the project results and major events. Releases are distributed to media outlets and journalists in the case study countries and to international media.

Media pitches

In addition to press releases, all the project partners can contact journalists and media outlets and pitch story ideas. KAS helps other partners to contact journalists and formulate the pitches.

5.7 Collaboration and interaction

Collaboration with other projects, networks, associations, and initiatives

GRETA will closely collaborate with projects, networks and other entities that work with the social aspects of the energy transition. The collaboration is managed through emails, meetings, workshops, and events by the project partners.

GRETA workshops and webinars

The project members organize workshops with the case study and other stakeholders to collect data, co-design and disseminate project results. The workshops are organized within certain tasks and by the project members responsible for those tasks.

GRETA organizes a webinar at the end of the project to present the project results to decision-makers. The webinar is organized by FhG with the support of other project partners.

The workshops and the webinar can be organized either as physical or virtual events.

5.8 Scientific publications

Open access scientific publications are produced to transfer knowledge and make the project results available for exploitation within the academic community. The scientific publications are published after the first year and within 18 months of the end of the project. The publications are sent to open-access academic journals and linked to the project website.

Scientific publications will be produced by LUT, TNO, UNIBO, FhG, GESIS, VPS, and TEC.

5.9 Policy briefs

GRETA will produce policy briefs at the end of the project. The briefs will be distributed to decision-makers through the EEAB, social media channels, the newsletter and in different events and workshops. FhG is responsible for producing and distributing the briefs.

5.10 Project partners' channels

In addition to GRETA's official communication channels and tools, all consortium partners use their organizations' channels, networks, and partnerships to advance the communication and dissemination goals of the project. This is done through sharing GRETA's content and communicating about GRETA in their channels, in events and workshops and interacting directly with their networks and partners.

6 Communication and dissemination activities

GRETA's communication and dissemination activities are divided into three partly overlapping stages: 1. Promoting the project, 2. Interacting with stakeholders and 3. Dissemination of results. The activity plans described in this section will be updated throughout the project.

6.1 Promoting the project

This stage includes activities that aim to make the project known among its most important stakeholders and target groups (Table 1). The activities are linked to objectives C1 and C2 that are described in Section 2.1, Communication objectives.

Table 1. Project promotion activities

Activity	Target group	Channel	Key messages	Schedule
GRETA launch	National and local media outlets, citizens, decision-makers	Press release, GRETA social media channels, GRETA webpage	What is GRETA?	M2
Local events in case study locations	Case study participants	Events	What is energy citizenship? What is GRETA? What is this case study about?	M2–
Social media campaign during EU Sustainable Energy Week	Academic community, decision-makers, media, NGOs, citizens	Twitter, LinkedIn	What is energy citizenship? What is its role in the energy transition? What is GRETA?	M6
Blog posts on energy citizenship, energy communities and GRETA	Citizens, decision-makers, businesses, academic community, NGOs	GRETA's webpage, newsletters, social media channel	What are energy citizenship and the objectives of GRETA?	M6–M17

"You've got the power" video	Case study participants, decision-makers, NGOs	Distribution through GRETA's channels	What is energy citizenship? What is GRETA?	M7
Media pitches about the case studies	National and local media, citizens	Personal contacts	What are the case studies about?	M8

6.2 Interacting with stakeholders

This stage includes activities that aim to create understanding and engage stakeholders with the project (Table 2). The activities are linked to objectives C2 and D1– 3 that are described in Section 2.1, Communication objectives and Section 2.2, Dissemination objectives.

Table 2. Interaction activities

Activity	Target group	Channel	Key messages	Schedule
Updates on the project's development	Citizens, decision-makers, businesses, academic community, NGOs	Distribution through GRETA's channels, face-to-face meetings	What is currently happening in GRETA?	Ongoing
Participation in non-academic events, such as EU Sustainable Energy Week, European Innovation Summit, World Sustainable Energy Days, BEHAVE: European Conference on Behavior and Energy Efficiency and World Energy Week	Businesses, decision-makers, NGOs	Event participation, GRETA's social media channels	What is energy citizenship and why does it matter? What is GRETA and how does it benefit the stakeholders?	Ongoing

Participation in academic conferences, such as the International Conference on Applied Energy, EU-SPRI Conference, International Conference on Energy Research and Social Science	Academic community	Event participation, GRETA's social media channels	What is currently happening in GRETA? What are the preliminary results? What is happening in other energy-related research projects and are there possibilities for collaboration? Which other projects could benefit from GRETA?	Ongoing
Collaboration with other projects, networks, associations & initiatives	Decision-makers, businesses, academic community, NGOs, non-profits	Workshops, meetings, one-on-one communication	What GRETA can benefit from other projects and how can GRETA help them in their work?	Ongoing
GRETA workshops and webinar	Decision-makers, businesses, academic community, case study participants	Workshops, webinar, GRETA's webpage, newsletters, social media channels	What is energy citizenship, and how can it best be promoted?	Final year

6.3 Dissemination of results

This stage includes activities that aim to inform and discuss the project results with the stakeholders (Table 3). The activities are linked to objectives D1– 4 that are described in Section 2.1, Dissemination objectives.

Table 3. Dissemination activities

Activity	Target group	Channel	Key messages	Schedule
Research articles and special issues on GRETA's project results	Academic community	Scientific publications	What are the key results of project GRETA?	After the first year of the project

				start and within 18 months of project end
Information and policy recommendations on how energy citizenship can be promoted to support the clean energy transition	Decision-makers	Policy briefs and meetings	Ways to promote energy citizenship	Final year
Publication of GRETA's main project results	National and local media outlets, citizens, decision-makers, academic community	Press release, GRETA social media channels, GRETA webpage, webinar	What are the key results of GRETA?	Final year
"Pathways to energy citizenship" video of the project results	Citizens, decision-makers, businesses, academic community, non-profits	Distribution through GRETA's channels	What are the key results of GRETA?	Final year
Information on different energy behaviors and Strategies	Citizens	Distribution through GRETA's channels, workshops	How can I become an active energy citizen?	Final year

7 Social media strategy

Social media plays an important role in GRETA's stakeholder engagement, communication, and dissemination activities. The project uses multiple social media channels to reach out to different target groups and stakeholders. The channels are listed in Section 5.2, Social media.

7.1 Objectives, target groups and metrics for social media channels

Table 4 lists all social media channels used in GRETA's communication and dissemination. The channels are linked to objectives described in Sections 2.1, Communication objectives and 2.2, Dissemination objectives.

Table 4. Social media objectives, target groups and metrics

Channel	Primary target group	Objective	Metrics followed
Twitter: @ProjectGreta #projectgreta	Decision-makers, media, NGOs, networks, academic community	C1–2, D1–2	Followers Likes Engagement Hashtag reach
LinkedIn: Project GRETA	Businesses and the industry	C1–2, D1–2	Connections Views Engagement
Facebook group: "GRETA community"	Case study participants	C1–2, D1–2	Members Engagement
ResearchGate: project profile	Academic community, networks	D4	Followers
YouTube channel	Case study participants, national and local media outlets, citizens	C1–2, D1–2	Views
Project members' social media accounts	All above	C1–2, D1–2, D4	Views Engagement Followers

7.2 Content types

Table 5 lists content types and activities planned for GRETA's social media channels.

Table 5. Social media content types

Type of content	Channel(s)	Schedule
Sharing of energy citizenship related materials produced by others	Twitter, LinkedIn	Once a week
Sharing of GRETA blogs, news and materials published on the project website	Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook group	Twice a month
“What is energy citizenship?” series: visualized posts about energy citizenship	Twitter, LinkedIn	M6
“Stories of energy citizenship” series: short interviews and quotes from case study participants and other stakeholders	Twitter, LinkedIn	Once a month
Polls and discussions on chosen themes	Facebook group	Once a month
“You’ve got the power” video: a 1 to 2 minutes long animated story about the project	YouTube	M7
Sharing of research articles, presentations, and deliverables	ResearchGate	Ongoing
Live interviews or panel discussions with GRETA partners and stakeholders	Twitter	Final year
“Pathways to energy citizenship” video: a 2 to 3 minutes long video about the project results	YouTube	M30

8 Exploitation strategy

This section describes GRETA's exploitation strategy. It includes elements that are shared among all the project partners but also activities that are part of the partners' individual exploitation plans.

8.1 Domains of exploitation

The exploitation activities of GRETA will be mainly created under four domains: further research, education, policy change and societal change. These domains correlate with the exploitation objectives described in Section 2.3, Exploitation objectives.

Further research

The research results of GRETA create new knowledge regarding the energy citizenship phenomenon and its impact on the energy transition.

Education

The academic partners of the project will disseminate and exploit the project results through the education they offer to future professionals of the energy-related issues and climate-neutrality.

Policy change

GRETA aims at creating policy change through contributing to new policies and regulations that embrace and encourage the energy citizenship phenomenon.

Societal change

GRETA aims to create societal change among and through its case study participants: active energy citizenship behaviors and citizen-led initiatives.

8.2 Joint exploitation strategy

This joint exploitation strategy (Table 6), including individual exploitation strategies by the project partners, will be updated throughout the project but especially during the final year.

Most of the exploitation actions will be aimed towards scientific exploitation. However, the project will have two main exploitable outputs: GRETA OPCE and policy recommendations. The GRETA Open Portfolio for Civic Energy Empowerment (OPCE) gathers all the data, frameworks and roadmaps created during the project. The OPCE

is linked to the project website and made permanently available for all interested stakeholders. The policy recommendations will be created together with decision-makers and shared with all stakeholders in a webinar to be organised at the end of the project.

Table 6. Exploitation strategy

Domain	Objective	Means or channels	Schedule	Responsible partner(s)
Further research	E1	GRETA OPCE, scientific publications, conferences, ongoing and further research projects	After the first year of the project	LUT, UNIBO, TNO, FhG, VPS, TEC, GESIS
Education	E2	University courses, thesis supervision	Final year and after the project	LUT, UNIBO
Policy change	E3	Policy recommendations, seminars, workshops, participation in policy discussions and boards	Ongoing	FhG, LUT, UNIBO, KAS
Societal change	E4	GRETA community, policy discussions, support for local initiatives, commercial solutions	Final year and after the project	FhG, UNIBO, VPS, TEC, KAS

9 Indicators of success

This section describes the indicators that GRETA follows to ensure successful communication, dissemination, and exploitation. The measures (Table 7) correlate with the objectives described in Sections 2.1, Communication objectives; 2.2, Dissemination objectives, and 2.3, Exploitation objectives. The measures are monitored and reported by KAS.

Table 7. Indicators of success

Channel	Objectives	Measures of success
Project website	C1, D1, D4	1,000 unique site visitors per month (by the end of the project)
Media communication	C1, D2	More than 25 appearances on national/international media
Social media: a) Twitter b) LinkedIn c) Facebook community d) YouTube e) ResearchGate	C1, D1–2	a) 300 followers on Twitter b) 150 followers on LinkedIn c) 100 members in Facebook group d) more than 200 views per video on YouTube e) 100 followers in ResearchGate
Academic events	C1–2, E1	10 to 20 conference participations, 2 academic workshops or discussion events organized or co-organized by the consortium at national or international conferences
Non-academic events	C1–2	Participation in at least 2 EU events, 4 industry events and 4 community events
Collaboration with other projects, networks, associations, and initiatives	C1–2	Collaboration with more than 5 projects, networks, associations, and initiatives
Stakeholder workshops and a policymaker webinar	C2, D3, E3	More than 7 people attending each workshop More than 10 people participating in the policymaker webinar
Scientific publications	D4, E1–2	8 to 15 journal publications in top-tier journals and conferences, one special issue on energy citizenship in a top-tier journal
Policy briefs	D1, D4, E3	Up to 8 bilateral meetings with policymakers leading to at least 6 policy briefs

Printed promotional materials
Brochures
Roll-ups

C1, D1

- a) More than 200 brochures delivered to the stakeholders
- b) Roll-ups presented in all GRETA's physical events

10 Conclusions

This deliverable presented GRETA's Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy. Its nine sections defined the objectives, target groups, channels, means and indicators for successful research project communications. It also included a separate social media strategy and an exploitation strategy.

The strategy introduced GRETA's CDE objectives, key message, tone-of-voice, target groups and channels. As shown, GRETA's communication and dissemination activities can be divided into three stages. Stage 1 includes activities linked to project promotion, and these activities are mostly produced during the first half of the project lifetime. Stage 2 focuses on stakeholder interaction throughout the project. The interaction is carried out through meetings, events, and workshops. Stage 3 aims to disseminate the project results effectively through scientific publications, policy briefs and events.

GRETA's social media strategy focuses mainly on project promotion and dissemination. GRETA's main social media channels are Twitter and LinkedIn, which are supported by YouTube and Facebook.

Exploitation of the project results is done through four domains: further research, education, policy change and societal change. The exploitation strategy will be updated during the final year of the project.

This strategy will be updated when needed by KAS together with the project partners.